

EDUCATION AND CAREER GUIDANCE CAPACITY BUILDING NEEDS OF TEACHERS OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCE AS A TOOL IN COUNSELLING THE STUDENTS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN A DEPRESSED ECONOMY

Lawal, O. Isaac (PhD)

And

Onipede Omoleye (PhD)

And

Lukman Ibrahim Jahun

And

Attahiru Zubairu

Faculty of Education

Federal University Kashere, Gombe State.

Abstract

This study was carried out to determine the education and career guidance capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science in counselling the students in agricultural careers for sustainable development in a depressed economy. The study was carried out in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State. Three research questions were developed for the study. The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study was one hundred (100) teachers of agricultural science in senior secondary schools in Dukku Local Government Area. The entire population was used for the study due to the manageable size. The instrument for data collection was titled career guidance for counseling students for sustainable development (CGCSSD) questionnaire which was face validated by three experts. Cronbach Alpha method of reliability was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and it yielded a coefficient of 0.82. The questionnaire were administered on the respondents and the entire questionnaire were retrieved. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviations to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that fifteen (15) items on students awareness of teachers of agricultural science as career teaches, fourteen (14) items on problems facing teachers of agricultural science and twelve (12) items on capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science for effective performance of their jobs were all agreed upon. Recommendations were made to the Ministry of Education in Gombe State to organize capacity building, conferences and workshops to enhance effective career guidance programme in secondary schools. Also students should be motivated to seek for career guidance from their teachers of agricultural science in order to make the right career decision for sustainable development in this era of economic depression.

Introduction

Education is a powerful weapon for the development of an individual and the nation in general. It is believed that no nation can develop socially, economically, politically and technologically without education. Education as defined by Dewey in Eduhutch (2021) as the development of all those capabilities in the individual which will enable him to control his environment and fulfill his responsibilities. Nunn in the same Eduhutch (2021) explained that education is the complete development of the individuality of the child so that he can make an original contribution to human according to the best of his capacity. In order to acquire education or be educated, the individual has to go to school where he will be taught morally academically and in other areas of human development before the individual can be useful for himself and the society.

The teaching of the individual occurs in the school by a teacher. When it comes to the duty of guiding the secondary school students in career choice, it is directly the work of a professionally qualified teacher of agricultural science. A teacher of agricultural science as explained by Olaitan, Asogwa and Assouzu in Lawal (2013) Is an individual who is trained in pedagogical and technical areas of agricultural science and is charged with the responsibilities of imparting knowledge, skills and attitude to students.

AgCareers (2023) stated that teachers of agricultural science are responsible for the

education of agriculture, food science and natural resources to the students. They give vital skills that are important in agricultural industry to the students. The author outlined some responsibilities of teachers of agricultural science as follows:

1. Conducting an instructional programme that educates the students about their career pathway
2. Enhancing youth leadership in free future farmers
3. Providing knowledge and skills necessary to compete in global economy
4. Overseeing Supervised Agricultural Experience Programme (SAEP) of students
5. Supervise and maintain school laboratory (farm, feeding centre, green house, meat laboratory) used for students SAEP among others. A teacher of agricultural science in this study is an individual trained pedagogically and technically to impart knowledge, skills and attitudes to students in agriculture and at the same time guide the students in their career pathway in order to make the right career choice. With the modern technology and internet facilities if a teacher of agricultural science must perform his job effectively he needs capacity building.

Capacity building according to United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (2021) is the

process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts, abilities process and resources that organizations and communities (or individual) need to survive, adapt and thrive in a fast growing world. It is a process of improving the ability of a person, group, organization or system to meet the objectives or perform better. Asogwa, Dumbri and Omeje (2010) explained that capacity building is the act of developing the level of knowledge, skills and attitude possessed by an individual in a given job to maximize profit and enhance income (Asogwa, Dumbri and Omeje 2010). Wikipedia (2023) explained that capacity building is the improvement in an individuals or organizations facility (or capability) to produce perform or deploy. Capacity building in the context of this paper is the process of equipping teachers of agricultural science with the understanding, knowledge, skills, attitudes and access to current information and training that will enable the individual to be proficient and perform well in the task of guiding students in making the right and unregrettable career choice.

Career is a job which an individual does for payment or reward. Hornby (2023) stated that career is synonymous with work, job trade, occupation or profession. Akintola in Lawal (2013) explained that the role

of teachers of agricultural science in guiding students is characterized by the fact that the youth have problems in decision making while they are yet in secondary schools and after leaving the school. Teachers of agricultural science has the role of guiding the students in choosing appropriate subjects and provide them with career or occupational information. In the opinion of Arthur in Ezeji (2001), career guidance has the following activities that teachers of agricultural science should perform. They include: assisting the students to acquire knowledge of the characteristics, functions, duties and rewards available in a career; making them to understand general and specific abilities as well as the qualifications, age, sex, e.t.c required for a group of careers; providing for in and out of school career or work experiences through try-out courses and vacation jobs to familiarize the students with the career conditions with a view to sharpening the students interest and abilities; view honest labour as worthy. All these activities are important for teachers of agricultural science and that is why they need capacity building in career guidance with the current dispensation of global technological advancement.

This will lead the students to be self employed, have honest jobs, become employers of labour, see dignity in

labour, become happy, raise their standards of living, contributes their own quota to the society and national economic growth in an on-going depressed economy.

However career guidance teachers face a lot of challenges that have impeded their progress towards guiding the students in making the right career choice. Simran (2023) listed some challenges and problems of career guidance counselors as follows: inadequate time for career counseling to students, lack of regular trainings, heavy workload on career counseling teachers, non cooperation of students and lack of funds. In the opinion Olusegun (2023) outlined the followings as problems facing career counseling teachers. They are: lack of professional career guidance teachers, lack of requisite support, lack of fund, poor perception of career teachers, non cooperative attitude of principals, teachers and lack of time. To solve these problems there is the need for teachers of agricultural science to effectively guide the students in making the right career decisions, and be fully employed, increase their living standard in a depressed economy.

Economic depression according to Nathan (2023) is a downturn in economy, it is a period where

economic activity suddenly declines, unemployment skyrockets, production slows down and there is drastic and sustained drop in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Daniel (2023) stated that depressed economy is a severe and prolonged downturn in economic activity. It is an extreme recession that leads to a decline in Gross Domestic Product with the symptoms of sharp fall in economic growth, employment and production. The author went further to itemize the factors that characterize depression as follows:

- i. Substantial increase in unemployment
- ii. A drop in available credit from banks
- iii. A diminishing output and productivity
- iv. Falling currency values
- v. Consistent negative GDP growth
- vi. Oil price hikes
- vii. Sovereign debts defaults
- viii. Loss of consumers confidence
- ix. Stock market crash
- x. Bankruptcies
- xi. Reduced trade and global commerce etc

In an attempt to avoid the excruciating pain of depressed economy in our nation by secondary school students, they need to be rightly guided in choosing their future career. It was observed by the researchers through one –one discussion and oral

interview that the students of agricultural science in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State lacked career information to enable them perform better in the world of work. While at school, they find it difficult to select the subjects that will lead to their career choice. Another problem is the lack of adequate and proper guidance services which ought to have been given to them by the school through their teachers of agricultural science who have been educated and trained in career guidance courses. It was also noticed that some principals failed to cooperate with the teachers in supporting a career guidance programmers in schools. This has made these agricultural science students to make wrong career choice which eventually led to failure and poor performance as explained by those who have graduated from secondary schools in the area of the research. The identified problems has made the researchers to find out the capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science in guiding the students to make the right career choice in an era of this depressed economy for sustainable development.

Sustainable development according to International Institute for Sustainable Development (2023) is the development that meets the needs of present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. The aim of sustainable development is to balance our economic, environment and social needs, allowing prosperity for now and future generations. Linus (2023) reported that the United Kingdom has recognized

four objectives of sustainable development. These include social progress and equality; environmental protection; conservation of natural resources and stable economic growth. This can be achieved by reducing pollution, poverty and unemployment. Poverty and unemployment can be reduced through proper career guidance and right career choice.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study therefore was to determine the education and career guidance capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science in guiding the students for sustainable development in a depressed economy in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State specifically the study sought to

1. Determine the level of awareness of senior secondary school in knowing that teachers of agricultural science are career guidance personnel's.
2. Find out the problems facing the teachers of agricultural science in conducting effective career guidance programmes for senior secondary school students
3. Determine the capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as career guidance teachers in Dukku Local Government Area for sustainable development in a depressed economy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the level of awareness of senior secondary school students in Dukku Local Government Area in knowing that teachers of agricultural science are career guidance personnel's?
2. What are the problems facing the teachers of agricultural science in conducting effective career guidance programmes in senior secondary schools in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State?
3. What are the capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as career guidance teacher in Dukku Local Government Area for sustainable development in a depressed economy?

High Awareness / Highly Needed

Moderate Awareness / Averagely Needed

Little Awareness/Slightly Needed

No Awareness/Not Needed

The response options had a corresponding value of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The questionnaire was validated by three experts from the Department of Science Education (Agricultural Education Unit). The experts were asked to determine its validity to ensure that the items were capable of measuring what they were supposed to measure. Their corrections were used to develop the final questionnaire used for the study. Cronbach Alpha reliability formula was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82.

Hundred (100) copies of the questionnaire were administered on the respondents and all were retrieved and analyzed using mean and standard deviations to answer the research questions. The real limit of numbers was used to take a decision on the questionnaire items for research questions one and three. The real limit of the response options were as follows:

- i. High Awareness /Highly Needed =3.50-4.00
- ii. Moderate Awareness/ Averagely Needed =2.50-3.49
- iii. Little Awareness /Slightly Needed=1.50-2.49
- iv. No Awareness/ Not Needed = Less than 1.50

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for the study, the study was carried out in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State. The population of the study was 100 teachers of agricultural science in Dukku Local Government Area Senior Secondary schools. The census technique was adopted as the number of respondents was small and manageable and therefore no sampling. Three research questions were developed for the study. A-41 structured questionnaire items titled career guidance for counseling students for sustainable development (CGCSSD) were used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire items were developed from literature review and used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into four response options as follows

Any item whose mean is 1.50 and above was regarded being aware (awareness), and Needed while any item whose mean is less than 1.50 was regarded as No awareness, and Not needed.

For research question (2), the data collected were analyzed using weighted mean and standard deviation to answer the research question. The Arithmetic mean value is $4+3+2+1 = 10/4 = 2.50$. The 2.50 obtained was used as the cut off point for decision making. Any item whose mean value is 2.50 and above was regarded as agreed while those with the mean value below 2.50 were regarded as disagreed.

The standard deviation was used to determine the closeness or otherwise of the opinion of the respondents from the mean. A low standard deviation indicates that the

respondents tend to be very close to the mean whereas high standard deviation indicates that the respondents were very far from the mean.

Results

The results for this study were obtained from the research questions answered through the data collected and analyzed.

Research Question 1

What is the level of awareness of senior secondary school students in Dukku Local Government Area in knowing that teachers of agricultural science are career guidance personnels?

The data for answering research question 1 are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Mean ratings of the responses of teachers of agricultural science in Dukku Local Government Area on level of awareness of senior secondary school students in knowing that the teachers of agricultural science are career guidance personnels.

N=100				
S/N	Items Statement	\bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Remarks
1.	Are you aware of the existence of teachers of agricultural science as a career guidance counsellor	3.67	0.66	HA
2.	Are you aware of the services rendered by teachers of agricultural science in relation to career opportunities	3.61	0.68	HA
3.	Do you have any awareness pertaining to a yearly career counseling day in your school	3.65	0.67	HA
4.	Do the school allocate specific time for career talk termly	3.61	0.70	HA
5.	Any awareness about students been helped to choose the correct subjects for their future career	3.85	0.49	HA
6.	Are you aware that teachers of agricultural science can expose you to the world of work	3.58	0.73	HA
7.	Do the teachers of agricultural science cooperate	3.63	0.72	HA

with other guidance counselors in the school

8.	How about the school principals support for the teachers of logistics for career counseling programmes	3.59	0.71	HA
9.	Do the teachers of agricultural science invite guest speakers to talk to students about different career opportunities	3.71	0.58	HA
10.	Are you aware through the guidance of teachers of agricultural science that your interest, ability, intellectual emotion e.t.c play a role in choosing a career	3.57	0.79	HA
11.	Are you aware that career guidance can help you in your time management and how to cope with school life	3.55	0.81	HA
12.	Are you aware that career guidance can help to remove your fear pertaining to your future career	3.85	0.49	HA
13.	Do you think career counselling by the teachers of agriculture is beneficial to students	3.58	0.73	HA
14.	Are you aware of the necessity of students to consult the career guidance teacher when making their career decisions	3.67	0.65	HA
15.	Are you aware that career guidance to students can solve the problem of unemployment in our country	3.61	0.70	HA

Key : \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents, HA=High Awareness

The data presented in Table 1 revealed that the fifteen (15) awareness items on the level of awareness of senior secondary school students had their means ranged from 3.55 to 3.85 and they were above the real limit of 2.50 indicating that the senior secondary school students in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State were aware that agricultural science teachers are career guidance personnels.

The standard deviation of the fifteen (15) awareness item ranged from 0.49 to 0.81 and were low indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and from one another in their responses.

Research Question 2

What are the problems facing the teachers of agricultural science in conducting effective career guidance programmes in senior secondary schools in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State?

Table 2: Mean ratings of the responses of teachers of agricultural science on the problems facing the teachers of agricultural science in conducting effective career guidance programmes in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State. N=100

S/N	Items Statement	\bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Remarks
1.	Lack of professional career guidance teachers of agriculture of agriculture schools	3.84	0.36	Agree
2.	Lack of requisite support to career guidance counselors	3.63	0.59	Agree
3.	Lack of funds	3.47	0.68	
4.	Poor perception of the career guidance teacher by the school principals	3.49	0.67	Agree
5.	Non cooperative attitudes by other teachers to career guidance teachers	3.78	0.53	Agree
6.	Inadequate time for career counseling to students	3.52	0.72	Agree
7.	Non cooperative clients (students)	3.64	0.60	Agree
8.	Inadequate parental support for career guidance counselors	3.59	0.51	Agree
9.	Lack of regular trainings for career guidance counselors	3.64	0.64	Agree
10.	Heavy workload on career guidance counselors (Teaching and career guidance)	3.60	0.62	Agree
11.	Negative attitudes of students to career guidance (interested in getting-rich-quick syndrome)	3.71	0.51	Agree
12	Refusal of the school heads to organize career guidance talk for students	3.63	0.59	Agree
13.	Non declaration of a day for annual career guidance programmes	3.56	0.49	Agree
14	Non cooperation of other guidance counselors with career teachers of agricultural science	3.44	0.72	Agree

Key: \bar{X} = Mean, SD= Strongly Agree; A= Agree

Data in table 2 showed that the fourteen (14) items on the problems facing the teachers of agricultural science in conducting effective career guidance programmes had their means ranged from 3.44 to 3.84 and they were above the real limit of 2.50 indicating that all the fourteen (14) items on the problems facing teachers of agricultural science in Dukku Local Government Area were agreed upon.

The standard deviations of the fourteen (14) items on the problems facing teachers of agricultural science for effective career

guidance programmes ranges from 0.36 to 0.72 and were indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and from one another in their responses. This added some values to the reliability of the mean.

Research Question: 3

What are the capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as career guidance teacher in Dukku Local Government Area for sustainable development in a depressed economy

Table 3: Mean ratings of the responses of teacher of agricultural science on the capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as career guidance teachers in Dukku Local Government Area for sustainable development in a depressed economy.

N=100

S/N	Item Statements: Ability to	\bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Remark
1.	Guide the students in the selection of subjects that will lead to their desired career in agriculture	3.82	0.58	CBN
2.	Educate the students on how to recognize their interest, aptitudes, abilities and make effective use of them in choosing a career in agriculture	3.75	0.62	CBN
3.	Conduct counselling interviews for students in order to know their interest in area of agriculture	3.71	0.64	CBN
4.	Interprete the data available in relation to different agricultural career opportunities for each student	3.64	0.72	CBN
5.	Use students records of academic progress to get background information on students in order to help them in selecting agricultural career where they will excel	3.62	0.72	CBN
6.	Plan cooperatively with the school counselor, principal and other teachers on the issue of students career choice in agriculture	3.62	0.72	CBN
7.	Invite an experts in agricultural science careers	3.57	0.79	CBN

	to give a talk to Students during career day			
8.	Relate with students families to support their children's career aspirations in agriculture.	3.57	0.81	CBN
9.	Locate sources of acquiring knowledge, skills, characteristics functions, duties and rewards of available career in agriculture.	3.55	0.81	CBN
10.	Guide the students on where to get information on vocational training facilities in various institutes, their admission requirement, cost and length of trainings for their desired careers in agriculture.	3.54	0.80	CBN
11.	Locate sources of fund for economically handicapped students in order to obtain financial aid for furthering their career education in line with their desired career in agriculture.	3.68	0.69	CBN
12	Let them know various careers in agriculture (crops, Animal, Agribusiness Agric engineering e.t.c) which will make them to decide which career to choose in relation to their interests and abilities	3.71	0.64	CBN

Key: \bar{X} – Mean, CBN = Capacity Building Needed

Data in table 3, revealed that the twelve (12) items on the capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as career guidance teachers had their means ranged from 3.54 to 3.82 and they were above the real limit of 2.50 indicating that all the twelve (12) items on capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as career guidance teachers in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State were needed for sustainable development in a depressed economy the standard deviations of the twelve(12) items on capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as

career guidance teachers ranged from 0.58 to 0.81 and were low indicating that the respondents were close to the mean and from one another in their responses. This added some values to the reliability of the means.

Discussion of Results

From the study it was shown that all the fifteen (15) items on the level of awareness of the senior secondary school students in knowing that the teachers of agricultural science are career guidance personnel's revealed that the students were aware of

teachers of agricultural science as career personnels.

The items include whether they were aware that teachers of agricultural science are career guidance teacher, whether there is specific time for career guidance whether there is annual career day and whether the principal support the teachers of agricultural science as career guidance personnels.

The findings of this study is in agreement with the work of Kehinde (2019) who studied students awareness of school counseling services in Nigeria between 2017 and 2019 where it was found out that the students had high awareness level of counseling services. The findings of the author justified the findings of this study.

The result in Table 2 revealed that all the fourteen (14) items on the challenges facing the teachers of agricultural science in conducting effective career guidance programmes were agreed upon in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State. The problems include lack of funds, poor perception of career guidance teacher by the principals and other teachers, inadequate time for career counseling and heavy workload on career guidance teachers. This is in line with the submission of Olusegun

(2023) who outlined the problems of guidance counsellors in school and therefore suggested ways to solve them. Also, the study is in agreement with the work of Simran (2023) who analyzed the challenges and problems of guidance counseling teachers where it was found out that the problems analyzed by the author also confirmed the findings of this work. The views of the authors cited above justified the findings of this study.

The finding in Table 3 showed all the twelve (12) items on the capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science were necessary or needed by career guidance teachers in Dukku Local Government Area of Gombe State for sustainable development in a depressed economy. The area where capacity building needs are necessary are: guiding the students in subject selection conducting counseling interviews, interpretation of data among others.

The study is in consonance with the research conducted by Onaga and Oputa (2019) on capacity building skills required by technical college teachers in upholstery and machine woodworking trade for global competitiveness where it was found out that capacity building skills were required in

seven (7) items in upholstery and woodworking trade. The work of the authors cited above justify the findings of this study.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, only the items that met the real limit of 2.50 and above were regarded as agreed, aware and needed. The study successfully identified the level of awareness of students in relation to the job of teachers of agriculture as career guidance teachers. Also, problems facing teachers of agriculture that serve as hindrances in performing their career guidance duties effectively were identified and lastly capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science as career guidance teachers were identified. Despite the awareness of the senior secondary school students in Dukku Local Government Area, that teachers of agricultural science are also career guidance teachers, they fail to utilize the opportunities and therefore lacked career information that would have helped them to perform better in the world of work. If the right career decision is to be made by the students in order to reduce unemployment in this era of economic depression, the teachers of agricultural science needed capacity building trainings, workshops and seminars

to make them perform effectively and efficiently in their career guidance programmes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. Students should be motivated to seek for career guidance information from their teachers of agricultural science who are also trained career guidance teachers
2. The Ministry of Education in Gombe State should organize capacity building conferences, workshops and seminars in career guidance where the teachers of agricultural science could update their knowledge in the modern day career information, methods, and resources.

References

- AG Careers.com (2023), Agricultural science teacher- secondary. Retrieved from [agcareers.com/careers-profiles>agric](https://agcareers.com/careers-profiles/agric).
- Asogwa, V.C; Dumbri, D.N. & Omeje, M.N (2010) Competency capacity building needs of okra farmers for commercial production to enhance income in Enugu State. *Ebonyi*

- Technology and Vocational Education Journal* 1(1), 23-32
- Daniel, L (2023), Depression in the economy: definition and examples. Investopedia. Dotdash Meredith Publishing Limited.
- Eduhutch (2012) Definition of educations by different authors Accessed from eduhutch.blogspot.com>2021/07>de fi...
- Ezeji, S.C.O.A (2001) Guidance and counseling in education. Nsukka.Chulbson International Press.
- Hornby, A.S (2023), Oxford adance learners dictionary of current english. London Oxford University Press.
- IISD (2023), What is sustainable development? International Institute for Sustainable Development, III Lombard Avenue Suit 325 Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada R3BOT4
- Kehinde, C.L (2019), An Investigation of students awareness of school counseling services in Nigeria between 2017 and 2019. *Journal of Gender Information and Development in Africa* (JGIDA) 8(3)213-227
- Lawal, O.I (2013), Professional capacity building needs of teachers of agricultural science for effective instruction in secondary schools in Ondo State. Unpublished Phd project submitted to the Department of Vocational Teachers Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- Linus, W (2023), sustainabl environment. Retrieved from sustainable-environment.org.uk
- Nathan, P. (2023),What is economic depression? economic depression, history, characteristics and impact. Accessed from w.w.w.moneygeek.com
- Olusegun, I (2023) Problems of guidance and counseling in schools and solutions. Accessed from theselfdiscovery.com
- Onaga, P.O & Oputa, N.P (2019) Capacity building skills required by technical college teachers in upholstery and machine woodworking trade for global competitiveness *Journal of Association of Vocational and Technical Educations of Nigeria (JAUTEN)* 24 (1) 260-265
- Simran, K (2023) Challenges and problems of guidance and counseling. Punjab India, Accessed from educationsummary.com
- UNDP (2021) Capacity building political activity. United Nations Development Programme. International Programme. Encyclopedia Britannica.
- Wikipedia (2023) Capacity building. Accessed from en.m.wikipedia.org>wiki